

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADVERTISING AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIETY

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Abstract

The article examines the role, significance and influence of advertising on society. The main problems associated with this issue are also shown. Here are the results of the study, based on the analysis of which conclusions were drawn, from which it is clear that for 54% of respondents advertising is an integral part of their life. Also, the study revealed that 56% of respondents give preference to both the visual and informational aspects of advertising, this opinion is supported by the respondents' opinion regarding ideal advertising, which states that ideal advertising should not only provide information to the user, but also have an impact on him, to influence his willingness to purchase the product.

The article provides recommendations that companies will play an important role in advertising effectiveness.

Keywords: advertising is an integral part of life, advantage of advertising, ideal advertising, level of Georgian advertising.

Advertising is an integral part of our daily lives, be it television, print or online advertising. Because it helps people get acquainted with new products and build an image. In this regard, many questions can be asked: what is it intended for? What is its purpose? How does he try to achieve his goal? How reliable and accurate is the information it provides? Who is the advertisement aimed at: a buyer or a seller? Does it even matter? Do we take into account the information he provides? How does this affect society?

Depending on the purpose of advertising along with its many functions, it is important to say that it is a business tool whose purpose is to increase the sales and revenue of the company. And to do this, he needs to be able to convince a person that the advertised product will be ideal for the client and will exactly meet his needs. Advertising should provide people with as much information as possible about the client company so that with its help the company can get the desired name and reputation among people. Advertising should try to show people as much as possible the advantages of its product over the products of competing companies, but it cannot do this if no one trusts it. Therefore, the trust factor is very important, which can be obtained in different ways. People often like advertising to be authentic and transparent. In general, people gain confidence when they have reliable information about something. After all, the main purpose of advertising is to provide information, and it avoids this whenever possible. We draw attention to this opinion due to the lack of reviews for some advertised products. In advertising, they always try to emphasize the positive aspects of a particular product or service, to highlight what is good about this product. We can consider this using the example of the famous brand Coca-Cola. Its advertisements always say that it is tasty, healthy, in a can that is easy to drink, and they always show us happy faces, we see hired actors drinking this drink so deliciously that anyone will

want to buy it. Advertisements in most cases provide reliable information, but only positive information. Consider the Coca-Cola example again. Coca-Cola advertisements never mention the negative aspects of the drink. For example, the fact that Coca-Cola is a very common and useful remedy for removing rust from metal, that this drink has a very high sugar content, which is dangerous to health if consumed frequently and in large quantities, or that it also contains large amounts of caffeine, which causes getting used to this drink. Despite the fact that the vast majority of Coca-Cola consumers are aware of the mentioned disadvantages of this drink, they still continue to drink it. why Because there are factors that affect people psychologically. When we hear Coca-Cola, we all remember that the brand, which is more than a hundred years old, is still one of the leading companies in the market and is therefore very popular all over the world. Why? Because there are factors that affect people psychologically. When we hear Coca-Cola, we all remember that the brand, which is more than a hundred years old, is still one of the leading companies in the market and is therefore very popular all over the world. We see its advertising, and we feel so good that we no longer remember the negative aspects that we, in fact, know quite well. Coca-Cola spends most of its revenue on product advertising, which is why it is the largest and most profitable company in the market. In advertising, as I have already said, accurate information is conveyed in one way or another, but in addition to information, there are a number of factors through which advertising authors influence people's psychology. They use special techniques to attract and influence customers. Such techniques could be as follows:

- Emotional Appeals – Advertising that evokes emotions such as happiness, nostalgia, fear or empathy creates a strong connection between the consumer and him.

- Scarcity and urgency. Advertising that creates a sense of scarcity and urgency in the form of limited offers, exclusive offers or low inventory can quickly motivate consumers.

- Authority and expertise. Advertisements featuring influencers or experts in a particular field can increase confidence in the product or service being advertised.

- Visual and Verbal Cues – Advertising uses visual and verbal cues. These include: lighting, colors, images, motivational phrases and catchy slogans. The purpose of using these tools is to make advertising more varied, original and attractive to people and leave them with a memorable impression.

- Social proof – In advertising, we often see users of the advertised product expressing good feelings about it and recommending it. This is another factor that has a positive effect on a person's consciousness and helps to gain confidence.

- the so-called fear tactics – involves creating the illusion in the viewer that it seems necessary to purchase an advertising product.

As mentioned above, even though people know about the negativity of Coca-Cola, they still continue to consume it for the above reasons, but the cases where people fall for advertisements are not always so calm and peaceful. When people realize that an advertisement contains false information or hides the truth, they lose trust in the advertised company and its product. In more serious and problematic cases, the case may even end up in court due to dishonest advertising activities. Here I would like to mention two cases where such an incident took place [1].

The first story concerns Johnson & Johnson (J&J) and its talc. In 2018, J&J was sued over allegations that its powder contained asbestos, which causes ovarian cancer in women after regular use. Even though there was ample evidence of the real dangers of using this powder, advertisements continued to promote it without proper warning. This caused a lot of discontent, which cost the company \$4.7 billion [2].

The second case concerns the famous automobile company Volkswagen (VW). In 2015, he was embroiled in a scandal known as Dieselgate, where the company was found to have installed illegal software on its diesel vehicles designed to cheat emissions tests. The software allowed the car to emit fewer emissions during testing than under normal driving conditions.

And in advertising, its diesel cars were shown as an environmentally friendly product. This lie cost the company \$2.8 billion in financial losses and significantly damaged its reputation [3].

One way or another, advertising is an integral part of our daily life, we find it in various media: radio, television, print media, as well as on the streets in the form of outdoor advertising, on the Internet, on social networks. . Whether we like it or not, they still attract our attention. They always evoke certain emotions and form a certain impression about their product. Marketers try to make advertising as distinctive and attractive as possible, and for this they often create small songs, lyrics or slogans. We can give many examples from our reality, but here I would like to recall old Georgian advertising. The tech boom ad that you probably all remember well. Then, and not only then, we all laughed in our hearts at the lyrics of his outstanding song and at every show we watched with our eyes and ears, as if we were watching it for the first time. This advertisement was created eleven years ago, but no one has forgotten it until now, neither its distinctive visuals nor its texts, the very purpose of advertising is to attract people's attention, to be attractive and to provide information about the object of advertising.

The main goal of our topic was to study the influence of advertising on the population of the Imereti region. For this purpose, we conducted a field and online survey through a questionnaire throughout the city, in which about two hundred people took part. Their number was distributed by age as follows: 15-20 years old - 22%, 21-30 years old - 18%, 31-40 years old - 21%, 41-50 years old - 26%, 50+ years old - 13%. When asked how often they encounter advertising in everyday life, respondents' opinions are as follows: often – 54.1%, rarely – 28.2%, never – 17.6%. As the result of the study shows, 21 people out of 200 respondents do not watch advertising at all, which indicates that they do not trust the information conveyed in advertising. Also interesting is the result of the study showing what consumers prefer in advertising, from which it can be seen that 23.8% of respondents prefer an abundance of information in advertising about a product, 20.2% of respondents prefer the visual side. advertising, and 56% prefer both indicators. It seems that in order for advertising to be interesting, attractive and have an impact on the user, it must have both an abundance of information and a visual aspect (see figure 1).

Diagram 1.

In the study, there were interesting opinions regarding how often advertising attracts their attention. Here is an interesting opinion of the respondents:

- Advertising is the best way to communicate about yourself to people. When famous people advertise products or we are interested in buying advertised products, in such cases they attract our attention.
- A good advertisement produces a good impression on any person.
- Depending on my day, I can sometimes see it several times a day or not see it at all;
- Attention is drawn so often that it is broadcast on television or on the Internet.

It is also worth noting the fact that only a quarter of respondents answered the question, from which it became clear that advertising often attracts the attention of 51%, does not attract the attention of 19% and more or less 29%.

Also, the second quarter of respondents expressed an opinion on how popular Georgian advertising is. The following opinions were expressed on this matter:

- It is necessary to further improve this area. In some cases, an advertisement is perfect and provides all the necessary and necessary information about a product or any service, but most often we come across such advertisements, the visual part of which is better than what is presented. Although good advertising costs a lot of money to create, the content and quality of successful advertising is largely determined by knowing the proper techniques required to create it.

➤ There has been a clear improvement in recent years;

➤ Of course, some aspects need to be developed, but it can be said that he is at the peak of his calling;

In addition, 21% of respondents believe that Georgian advertising is at the peak of its popularity, 10% believe that it is not at its peak, and 19% believe that it is more or less at the peak of its popularity.

On another question regarding the ideality of advertising, which was answered by 38 respondents, their opinions were distributed as follows, namely:

- If the information presented in an advertisement is not devoid of reality and at the same time is presented clearly and openly, it is ideal.

➤ An ideal advertisement should convey well all the positive features of purchasing a product and should be completely tailored to the society we are offering.

➤ Advertising should not only convey information to the consumer, but also influence him, make him want to buy the product [4].

It is ineffective to interest the client and stimulate the desire to buy.

In our opinion, the most important and interesting part of the advertisement is its visual side. There is even such an expression «the eye eats and the eye drinks». It is the visual component of the advertisement that makes the first impression on a person, and only then does he decide whether to continue watching (or reading) the advertisement. This is the most diverse, special and easily memorable part of advertising. Advertising uses visual effects to attract people's attention, and then provides relevant information to an interested person. That's why its second most important component is the information it has to convey. It can be said that the information provided by the advertisement fully determines its content, purpose and visual aspect. The transmitted information should increase people's awareness of the advertising company and its product, without losing the desire to do it. In advertising, its main message should be conveyed briefly and clearly. It should be simple to understand, it should not tire the person and at the same time it should be able to motivate him.

As for the level of Georgian advertising, I think that it is really not up to par. As for television advertising, I don't even know when was the last Georgian advertisement that made people love it and remember it. Probably 10 or 12 years ago (advertising was especially popular: "Techno Boom", "Gurjaan Ice Cream", "Barambo", "Nabeghlavi" and others...). Time passes, everything develops, and it seems that Georgian advertising should have developed, but it did not work out. On the contrary... advertising is still accepted here, although it no longer has the originality and uniqueness that we liked. When it comes to print advertisements and posters, they attract people's attention less than television advertisements, but there are slight changes over time.

Advertising is an important business tool. It is needed by everyone and everything, by clients, because

they receive financial benefits, and by us, because we receive interesting and useful information from them. It affects us psychologically on a daily basis and we must use these effects and information as evidence and respond accordingly.

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